

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND SURGICAL OUTCOMES IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) remains one of the most frequent complications in abdominal surgery. Timely diagnosis and stratification of disease severity are essential for reducing mortality and postoperative complications. Understanding clinical predictors can optimize surgical outcomes.

Relevance: Acute adhesive intestinal obstruction (AAIO) remains one of the most frequent complications in abdominal surgery. Timely diagnosis and stratification of disease severity are essential for reducing mortality and postoperative complications. Understanding clinical predictors can optimize surgical outcomes.

Objective: To analyze the clinical profile and outcomes of patients with AAIO depending on the time of hospital admission and surgical approach.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective analysis was performed on 239 patients with AAIO treated between 2013 and 2024. Patients were grouped based on the year of treatment and the strategy used. Data included age, time to admission, previous surgeries, and intra-/postoperative complications. Statistical analysis included descriptive and comparative methods.

Results: Most patients (77.4%) were admitted more than 24 hours after symptom onset, with signs of dehydration and intoxication. Young adults (18–44.9 years) accounted for 46.9%, highlighting the social relevance of AAIO. Postoperative complications were more frequent in patients with multiple prior surgeries (17.6%). The most common surgical cause of AAIO was appendectomy (28%) and hernioplasty (22.6%). Earlier hospital admission was associated with a reduced rate of postoperative complications.

Conclusion: Delayed admission and multiple prior surgeries significantly increase the risk of adverse outcomes in AAIO. Early diagnosis and individualized treatment strategies are essential for improving prognosis.

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